

Teaching English to Kids: How to get kids interested and make and make learning fun

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Annotation

English is international language nowadays. It is very important to learn it from early age. Knowing of English language is necessary in every field of life. Through this article you will know how to teach children, what methods to use, how to make lessons interesting for kids, what kind of game you can play to practice the covered topic and new vocabulary. Also this article analyzes the extensive work being done on formation and strengthening of language learning skills in children.

Key words:

Language, field of life, practice, the covered topic, vocabulary, extensive.

Аннотация

Английский язык в настоящее время является международным языком. Очень важно научиться этому с раннего возраста. Знание английского языка необходимо во всех сферах жизни. Из этой статьи вы узнаете, как учить детей, какие методы использовать, как сделать уроки интересными для детей, в какую игру вы можете играть, чтобы практиковать пройденную тему и новую лексику. Также в данной статье анализируется большая работа, проводимая по формированию и укреплению навыков изучения языка у

детей.

Ключевые слова:

Язык, сфера жизни, практика, освещаемая тема, словарный запас, обширный.

Annotatsiya

Hozirgi vaqtda ingliz tili xalqaro tildir. Buni yoshlikdan o'rganish juda muhimdir. Ingliz tilini bilish hayotning barcha jabhalarida zarur. Ushbu maqolada siz bolalarni qanday o'rgatish kerakligini, qanday usullardan foydalanishni, darslarni bolalar uchun qanday qiziqarli qilishni, mavzuni va yangi lug'atni mashq qilish uchun qanday o'yin o'ynashni bilib olasiz. Shuningdek, ushbu maqolada bolalarda til o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish va mustahkamlash borasida olib borilayotgan ko'plab ishlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar:

Til, hayot sohasi, amaliyot, yoritilgan mavzu, lug'at, keng.

Introduction

Today, knowing of English is a mandatory skill for both adults and children. If earlier children were introduced to a foreign language only in high school, now they start when the child learns to speak. Now, anywhere you can find educational centers where they can teach children English or classes with a tutor at home for kids. You can find tutorials, cartoons and songs. Children at an early age need to be taught: answer questions about yourself, be able to greet someone, be able to talk about yourself, family, friend, describe your house or room. Perceive and understand the teacher's speech, read and understand small texts.

Common Topics For Kids

- Alphabet and phonics
- Greeting and introduction (Hello/ Goodbye/ What's your name?)
- Feelings and emotions (How are you?)
- Weathers (How's the weather)

- Colors (What color is it?)
- Numbers (How many? / How much is it?)
- Shapes
- Parts of the body
- Rooms of the house (Where is dad? – He is in the living room.)
- Clothes (Put on your jacket./ What is he wearing?.)
- Transportation (How do you come to school?)
- Telling the time (What time is it?)
- Sports (What are you good at?)
- Hobbies
- Days of the weeks (What day is it?)
- Countable and Uncountable Nouns (some / any)

Tips on How to Teach a Child English

- Keep it simple (This is especially important with beginners. Try to keep sentences simple and then build on it.)
- Keep it fun (We learn more when we are having fun. There are so many fun teaching resources to support ESL learning with many games and activities to conduct lesson in interesting way)
- Use a role-play (It is a great way to develop speaking skills. Students can practice their vocabulary in fun ways.)
- Use technology (Nowadays technology plays very important role in our life. Technology is a great way to get children engaged in a lesson. You can use many apps, interactive games, ppt lessons and other platforms.)
- Use English Holidays (They can help to create a fun classroom environment. This can give children to explore other culture)

child left in the middle then gets to call out the next instruction. This game can be easily adapted to suit the vocabulary the class is learning such as appearance, clothing, likes/dislikes, family members, holidays – it’s amazing!

- **Slam**

This is another flashcard game and it works best with small groups. Place all the flashcards on the floor and have the children gather around them. Then call out the name of the flashcard and have the children ‘slam’ their hands onto the correct card. The child whose hand is at the bottom of the pile – and is, therefore, the fastest – wins! Get them to keep their hands on their heads until you call out a word, so they don’t hover over the pictures!

- **Memory**

For this game, you need to have two sets of matching flashcards or a set of pictures and corresponding words. Simply place all the cards face down on the floor and have the children take turns picking two cards until they match a pair. Children love this game and I’ve found it engages even the most easily distracted students.

- **Bingo**

To play this you need a Bingo grid with pictures, words, or desired vocabulary (there are lots you can print for free on the internet) or you can make your own! Give each child a grid to mark off as you call out words – the first to get a row or to complete their grid is the winner. Make sure you check the winner’s grid to ensure they have matched the words correctly! This can be made harder by giving the children clues to the correct picture rather than the word itself.

- **Simon Says**

A classic (for anyone who grew up in the 90s!), this is a great game to get out that excess youthful energy and either warm-up the class at the beginning or wind-down at the end. It's also great for learning body parts and commands in a fun and engaging way. The basic premise is that the teacher stands at the front of the class and gives instructions to the students. If the instruction is preceded by the phrase 'Simon says', the students should copy the action (e.g. Simon says, hands on your head). If it isn't preceded by 'Simon says' then they shouldn't copy the action, and, if they do, they are out of the game. The last one in at the end wins! It sounds more complicated than it is but, trust me, the children catch on fast! You could make it even easier for your younger students and change it to 'teacher says' instead of 'Simon says', if you want!

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